

**The Roman Catholic Church,
Anusim, Barbadian Sephardim, the
Nidhe Israel, and Colonialism
Version Two (Revised)**

An awful omen

I said I would never write again, my heart lay broken, tormented, and hurt. Yet, I awoke, sweating, anxious, and afraid. I had a strange dream, it felt like a nightmare. I was Moses, wandering the desert — whispers illuminated my travels, sounding “Anusit,” “Anusit,” “Anusit.” I dreamt of Moses Tolanto and Isaac Brandon Lopez, but it was not of honor,

so-called 'kavod,' but of dread, a strange sensation, the feeling of loss. Isolated, alone, and in social exile from spaces I once tried to find refuge within, I presumed, perhaps, after all, I had finally gone mad. My mind had broken under the pressure, and I found myself in delusions of grandeur.

Me? Envisioning myself as Moses? What even is an Anusit? Moses Tolanto and Isaac Brandon Lopez have been dead for centuries. Yet, here my dreams torment me, the ancestors seem to call upon me, at least in principal, I could not stop in this wilderness, I could not believe myself, my truth, my heart, my yearning to be a lie, to be a manipulation, trickery, or opportunism, for I had been loyal, for I had been good, for I had held Israel with reverence and yet. Here, I continue to have nightmares of spiritual turbulence. Madness, finally, beckoned me, and I was compelled. The erasure was absolute, the denial was effective, the

forced Christianization of my intentions rang true... But I had a hunch, behind this dream perhaps lay a deeper calling, in parts prophetic and in parts subconscious. Perhaps not madness, but a fire that was unwilling to be squashed by tyrants.

The Ghettoization, Pogrom, Legal Persecution, and Cultural Erosion of Barbadian Sephardim

“Barbados, a small island of the Lesser Antilles, uninhabited when settled by the English in 1627. Jews began to arrive mainly as sugar specialists from Dutch Brazil a year later. In 1654 a Jewish community was founded and the synagogue Nidhe Israel was established. A second synagogue, Semah David,

was founded in Speightstown.

After the once British colony of Suriname passed to the Dutch, in 1667, many Jews moved to Barbados to retain their British citizenship. Barbados was the first British territory in which Jews obtained full political rights.

Many Jewish settlers engaged in sugar and coffee cultivation. While the British government considered Jews to be good businessmen and tradesmen, British merchants did not like the Jews and accused them of committing illegal business transactions.

Jews were accused of trading more frequently with the Dutch than the British merchants. In 1661, three Jewish traders in Barbados requested to establish trade routes between Barbados and Suriname (it was still a British colony); through this enterprise the Jews gained much wealth, but created more irritation among many British merchants.

On October 23, 1668, the Jews of Barbados were forbidden to engage in foreign or local retail trade. Jews were forbidden from purchasing slaves, and were forced into living in a Jewish Ghetto in Barbados. By the late 17th century there were two Jewish communities in Barbados, in Bridgetown and Speighstown, K. K. Semah David. By 1679, nearly 300 Jews lived in Barbados.

By 1679 the Jewish population had reached 300, and by 1750 between 400 and 500, all of the Spanish-Portuguese. All the discriminatory laws were removed by 1802, by the colonial government of Barbados and in 1820 the British Parliament also repealed the discriminatory laws.

During the 18th century, the Jewish community of Barbados continued to grow and become financially successful, although the Jewish congregation in Speighstown closed. Rabbi Raphael Hayyim Isaac Carigal served the community of Bridgetown from 1774 until his death in 1777.

Decrees levying special taxes on the Jews, prohibitions barring Jews from employing Christians as their plantation workers, and lack of civil rights prevented the Jews from having a comfortable life in Barbados.

The Speighstown community was destroyed in 1739 by a mob that burned the synagogue and drove the Jews out of town, a very unusual incident in the Caribbean. Bridgetown Jews gradually began to abandon the island for the island of Nevis, for England or New York. By 1848 only 70 Jews remained; in 1925 the last professing Jew died. Nidhe Israel was abandoned.”

Virtual Jewish World: Spanish-Portuguese Nation of the Caribbeans: La Nacion

A “lack” of civil rights refers to:

“1674: Jews are granted the right to give evidence in courts of law in cases involving other Jews.

- 1676: A special tax is imposed on the Jewish community.
- 1679: Jews are prohibited from having Christian servants.
- 1688: Jews are banned from employing Christians and from retail trade.
- 1708: Jews are granted the right to vote in Barbados, though this right was later rescinded.
- 1739: The Jewish community reaches its peak population of about 800.
- 1786: Jews are allowed to take oaths on the Hebrew Bible in court cases.
- 1802: The Jewish Naturalisation Act is passed, granting Jews full rights as British subjects in Barbados.
- 1831: Jews are granted full civil and political rights in Barbados.” – <https://sephardicgenealogy.com/jews-of-barbados/>

Interestingly, this recollection entirely neglects the ghettoization of Barbadian Sephardim from “SephardicGenealogy.com”, creating an archival discrepancy, very common when discussing Barbadian Sephardic History.

Valerie Sheppard

There was something that troubled me. The St. Patrick's Roman Catholic Church, particularly a woman who conducted extensive genealogical research and study. Her name is "Valerie Sheppard," a Trinidadian-born descendant of Barbadian Creole-Sephardim, particularly descended from the St. Patrick's Roman Catholic Church. I had always browsed the content on her website, but I had never truly stopped to read it. But this dream — this sequence — compelled me in some regard to pursue the Roman Catholic Church and, by extension, her research more closely. It was there that the truths long suppressed by an intentional cultural genocide had been laid bare.

The Barbadian Sephardic Jews who remained within Barbados became Anusim within the 1800s due to two hundred years of mistreatment, ghettoization, coercive religious “laws,” and intermarriage. In addition to this, the community of Sephardim residing within Barbados would be supplemented by immigrants from across the Caribbean and the Mediterranean, creating what manifests today as “Creole Jews.” Valerie Sheppard, perhaps aware, or unaware — if she has not undergone conversion to Judaism at some point — is a member of our esteemed group and has the halachic designation “Zera Israel.” While her research, studies, and stories are impressive, they carry a heavy trail of documentation, one that is not consistent for all Sephardic families, as my own is scattered; Vera, Lance (I), and Lance (II) are all buried in unmarked graves, where the Roman Catholic Church actively omits their true names and their descendants names either by negligence or

intention, but I will not accuse the Church; there will be enough accusations to go around as this essay progresses.

V. Sheppard notes the Anglicanization of a Portuguese ancestor's name from João within Trinidad, an intentional tactic utilised by Sephardim to escape persecution, which explains why some names would become blatantly "English" and "Anglophone" making it harder to trace genealogical heritage using face value analysis, rather than critical Contextualizations of that particular person's ancestry, this would then become noted in the original Nidhe Israel Museum Guide where it states the Sephardic Geneological contribution to would become unknown, as names would be anglicized:

"About Christina, we know that she was born in Trinidad on 8 April 1866, the eldest daughter of Presbyterian Portuguese immigrants. Her father was

João (anglicized John) Pereira from Portugal, and her mother was Antonia

Alexander, born in the island of Madeira.”

While Miss Sheppard contributes meticulous and precise genealogical research, I will bring Jewish history, Jewish law, and coercive colonial dynamics. First, I will begin by analyzing the heritage of one of her ancestors, and I will leave you, the viewer, to decide the ultimate facts, with full awareness of the gravitas of the implications of what occurred.

Sociopolitical Analysis of Coercive Catholic Colonial and Post-Colonial Dynamics

“In researching my family history, I discovered that my Barbadian great-great-grandfather Daniel Lobo had been active in the Sephardic Jewish community and the Nidhe Israel Synagogue in Barbados. That is, until he married a Christian woman named Elizabeth Frances Ann Stoute on 14 June 1870. Records show that he was baptized at St. Michael’s Cathedral in Barbados on the same day as his marriage.

By tracing Daniel’s Jewish ancestry, and with the help of Dutch resources, I am able to share this story of my Jewish, Portuguese, and Dutch ancestry.”

It would seem one of her ancestors, a righteous man by the name of Daniel Lobo, was active in the Sephardic Jewish community up until the 1870s; this would be forty years before the “last professing Jew” would perish, subsequently being buried in Westbury Cemetery, and officially marking the “end” of the Barbadian Sephardic Jewish community.

And yet, there is no mention, nor any implication, that this ancestor, Daniel Lobo, has migrated elsewhere. What occurred was a conversion to Catholicism. The question remains, why would a Jew who was active in the Sephardic community, fully aware of the implications of what a conversion would mean at that time for his Jewish identity, do so? The answer is anyone’s gamble, but my guess would be coercive religious stipulations and laws provided to marriage. I am not making the implication that this ancestor was not a true believer in Christ, but I am drawing into question the sudden nature of his Christianization, not

dissimilar to the wife of a Jewish man being converted to have a halachically Jewish child, although in this particular situation, it would seem the reverse would be the reality.

But my sociological hypothesis does not end here; there are many gems within her genealogical research that support the Catholicization of the Barbadian Sephardim, but it travels beyond just that.

“The history of my family and that of many other families seems to be intertwined in one way or another with religion. My family history includes Presbyterian ancestors in Madeira fleeing to Trinidad and Jewish ancestors in Portugal fleeing to Amsterdam because of religious persecution. In Barbados, my mother’s parents, Esmée and Garnet St. Hill, who were baptized in the Anglican Church, converted to Catholicism sometime circa 1928. From then on, all baptisms,

marriages, and funerals of my immediate family took place and are
recorded in Catholic churches.”

“St. Patrick’s Cathedral was central to family life for several generations.

My Trinidadian father was Presbyterian, but since my mother was Catholic, in order for the marriage to take place at St. Patrick’s in 1943, he was required to make a vow to raise his children in the Catholic faith.

I was educated at the Ursuline Convent, as were my mother, aunts,
siblings, and several cousins.”

Make note, this occurred fifteen years after the official collapse of the Nidhe Israel, which meant the Sephardic Jews who had married and thus converted to Catholicism for “whatever reason” were forced by spiritual vow to raise children in the Catholic Church. This would explain why my grandfather, Lance Neville King (II), was educated in

the Catholic Church, having been born circa 1930, two years after the death of “the last professing Jew.” In effect, this likely created generations of Crypto-Jews and culturally distinct Barbadian Anusim.

The Puzzle Pieces Align

Previously to having researched her work more in-depth, all I could make were hypotheses on the nature of our colonization, on why my mother, her family, and even I had been Crypto-Jewish. Why exactly were we so tied to religious structures, yet having not belonged to any of

them? Now, recall that I mentioned Isaac Brandon Lopez at the beginning of this essay; let us not forget the reality of his and his sister's situation.

Sarah Brandon Lopez, before undergoing conversion to Judaism in Suriname, had been baptized Anglican, the state religion of "Los Barbados." This was not by her own choice; she was underage, she was baptized shortly after her birth by compulsion to serve the Anglican overlords of the Barbadian State, until having been freed of this spiritual bondage through conversion in Suriname at age 13, then stripped of that freedom when it came time for Jewish emancipation in Barbados.

But one little detail many historical accounts do not mention is that the emancipation of Jews, Afro-descended Barbadians, and Catholics all

happened within the same century, decades, or closer apart, the exact timeline is: Jewish Emancipation in 1802-1820 (taking effect in 1831),

but this does not refer to Afro-Sephardic, or mixed Race Jews of African, Sephardic, and otherwise ancestry, Catholic Emancipation in

1834, and African Emancipation in 1834-1838. This then

contextualizes why Moses Tolanto printed coins that stated

“Emancipation without slavery.” He was likely speaking to his

Afro-Sephardic hermano i hermana, who would not only be banned

from conversion due to the colonial, Mahamdic proto-one-drop “no

negros” rule of the Nidhe but further marginalized through chattel

slavery, a unique evil that the Sephardim, my ancestors, of the colonial

era, arguably created within Barbados.

Miss Sheppard’s work is a gold mine of valuable genealogical research; it

mirrors my own family. There are many names that appear across

lineages, such as “Christina,” “Maria,” and variants of names like “Ann,”

and this is not localized; it exists across lineages noted within her research to be within Trinidad. Conducting my own research of the St.

Patrick’s Roman Catholic Church revealed the graves of many Catholicized Portuguese, those whose names would later be anglicized, misinterpreted, or misremembered.

The Colonial Legacy of Spiritual Slavery

Now, we dive further into the nature of the colonial bureaucracy with my own testimony, a myth concerning my name itself. When I was born,

I was not immediately named, and this was because I had to be “christened.” My mother at the time was a Jehovah’s Witness, so this provided a legal loophole where I did not have to undergo the process, in theory. My mother denies I was christened, but my father remains unsure; the reality is that they are both correct. I was symbolically christened, and that is why on my national security information, I am given “Christian Names.” The first three names, apart from my last name, are listed explicitly as Christian, but on no other document, especially my passport, is this the case. The colonial bureaucracy is malevolent; if taken at face value, the State of Barbados has claimed my

soul as a Christian despite a clear legal exemption from a forcefully
“anglicized” name. This would mean I could never keep a covenant
related to being a Jew because it was decided for me before I was born,
like in the case of Sarah Brandon Moses, and others before her, because I
was born with no religious freedoms in practice, only in principle. If
Halacha is consistently applied, what is the designation provided for this
bureaucratic transgression upon my soul and dignity?

For this is consistent, along with many other actions by Barbadian
Christian, Jewish, and bureaucratic systems, with cultural genocide,

which is explained as:

“Cultural genocide, or culturicide, is a concept first described by Polish
lawyer [Raphael Lemkin](#) in 1944, in the same book that coined the term

‘genocide.’”

[“Browne, Dallas L., Salem Press Encyclopedia, 2019:](#)

Cultural genocide is the deliberate and systematic destruction of a culture. It is not ethical to destroy the culture of another group of human beings or change it without their consent. Each culture should be judged by its own standards of excellence and morality, unless its cultural practices threaten to harm others physically or mentally.”

[“Treglia, G. \(2016\). Cultural genocide. In J. Mackenzie \(Ed.\), The encyclopedia of empire. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley.](#)

Cultural genocide, or ethnocide, is the attempted destruction of a group’s culture, religion, and identity. It is a coercive act imposed by a dominant group upon a weaker or minority group. Cultural genocide has been associated with imperialism and with settler-colonialism. It is particularly associated with forced religious conversion and with forced assimilation policies, including child removal and the outlawing of cultural expression.”

“The [Armenian Genocide Museum](#) defines ‘culturicide’ as ‘acts and measures undertaken to destroy [nations’](#) or [ethnic groups’ culture](#) through spiritual, national, and cultural destruction.”

Now, to me, it all makes sense. This explains exactly why we were never taught about Sephardic history in Barbados in primary school. It explains why the Nidhe Israel’s Executive Committee, and its predecessors, intentionally omitted the legacy and inheritance of local Creole-Jews from history, and it explains why euphemisms such as “Assimilation” and “Last Professing Jew” were utilized. It is all a systemic maneuver and a successful attempt at gaslighting us, stripping us of our heritage, and denying our existence to perpetuate what they currently possess. It is telling with the emancipation of the Catholic faith within Barbados came the direct, and definitive decline of the Barbadian Sephardim, the actions of the Catholic Church represents a

seductive, coercive form of cultural genocide, the weaponization of love to enforce the perpetuation their religion at the expense of the freedom of Jewish souls, it would the seem the inquisition had not ended in the early 19th century, it simply became smarter, less apparent, and much more spiritual.

And yet still, the Catholics themselves would only bring upon themselves the alleged ire of our Protestant overlords for housing such people:

“Originally built in 1848, St. Patrick’s was virtually destroyed by a fire in 1897, suspected to have been started by Protestant elements. A new cathedral church, however, was completed in 1899 and consecrated on August 23, 1903.”

To the Nidhe Israel

For the Barbadians, it may just be pure idiocy, but I am sure the president, who is a self-proclaimed “university educated” “master of history and all things Jewish,” despite being “secular,” knows the implications of what his community and his ancestors have done.

They want us to forget who we are; they want to be the only Jews on this island, and everyone is in on this business, except us. The Barbadian colonial legacy and modern Jewish institutions, such as the World Zionist Congress, uphold and are complicit in the cultural genocide of Barbadian Sephardim, and rarely does the Jewish world seem to care, because we’re compelled and born into this accursed system. No one cared to fact-check the narrative of the Nidhe Israel unless it directly affected their institution; no one cared to protect us institutionally, even if very fringe forums may debate our reality, thus there would be no

return for us from this fate we have been designated, and that legacy is
systemic.

My family, beyond my mother, remains distant, unsure, and unwilling
to interact with my findings. I am declaimed, lambasted as a fool, as a
Christian, as no true Sephard, as a heretic, as mentally unstable, and as
in need of therapy, Israel, or Chabad. Both of which, thus far, enable the
current system built on our backs, our torture, and our religious
submission.

To ask us to convert enables a system where we are forever locked out of
the gates of Zion and our Jewishness due to class, race, gender, and
ideology. But this should not be the case; if G-d held us true, we would
be declared halachically Jewish, and it would fix the years of our
spiritual desecration, the years of the secrets, the lies, the manipulations,

and the false narrative of “willing” Christian assimilation. If we were
allowed to be free, we would be.

If we were allowed to be free to choose at all times, then we would not
be beholden to halachic laws equivalent to one drop. We would not have
to jump through hoops to gain an inch of what is owed to us. And yet,
the Jewish world allows this desecration to happen; I have only heard
rumors of some synagogue in Britain fighting fiercely for our
self-determination, at least as far as artifacts are concerned.

To them, I say, the Nidhe Israel must NEVER have those artifacts, as
they are our oppressors, the same as the government, the same as the
Catholic Church, and the same as the Inquisition, and forevermore will
our torment be suppressed out of a need for money. While many of
them within the Nidhe gallivant across England and other territories to

portray their eternal social mobility, we have only tears left to remember

who we are.

An injustice so profound, it will never be acknowledged publicly, but I

have my own writ for the President of the Nidhe.

Cursed be him, Tyrant of the Nidhe Israel!

Cursed be he when he breathes, cursed be he when he speaks, cursed be

he when he enters el Esnoga Nidhe, cursed be he when he traverses el

Esnoga de Nidhe, cursed be he when he leaves the Nidhe, cursed be he

while he lives, and cursed be he in death.

I judge the President, his progeny, and his ancestors as faux-Nidhe

Esnoga de Yisrael — a tyrant, a liar, a thief, a manipulator, and above all,

a violator of the Anusim dos Nidhe de Yisrael! Hashem does not shine brightly on the unholy; the creator's justice and glory are eternal. It will be answered by the hands of time. Let it be known:

I spoke the truth, not lies, I brought facts, the Peddlers and their Progeny brought erasure, arrogance, and desecration. The liars are the benefactors, but not the victors! History will remember this, ever after!

<https://www.valsheppard.com/>

<https://sites.google.com/view/sephardic-king-family-barbados/home>

<https://sephardicgenealogy.com/jews-of-barbados/>

<https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/la-nacion>

<https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/barbados-virtual-jewish-history-t>

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